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Rye A Agar

 In 1 collection

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Abstract

This Agar medium can be used for the cultivation of *Phytophthora infestans*. It is particularly suitable for long term maintenance of *Phytophthora* on plate.

To induce sporulation Rye B agar is recommended.

This protocol has been copied from <http://www.plantpath.cornell.edu/Fry/>

Original reference: Caten, C. E. and J. L. Jinks. 1968. Spontaneous variability of single isolates of *Phytophthora infestans*. I. Cultural variation. Can. J. Bot. 46: 329-348.

Materials

MATERIALS

 Distilled Water

 Rye grains

 Agar

Troubleshooting

- 1 Soak 60 g of rye grain in distilled water for 24 hours at room temperature. This is done in a small tray so that water just covers grain. Cover tray tightly with aluminum foil.
- 2 Next day, pour supernatant off germinated grain and put aside.
- 3 Place grain in a beaker, add distilled water (about 1 inch above grain) and blenderize on high for 2 minutes. Cook in water bath for 1 hour at 68°C. Don't modify extraction time or temperature.
- 4 Filter through 4 thicknesses of cheese cloth squeezing gently to remove residual liquid. Discard cheese cloth and grain sediment.
- 5 Combine original supernatant (liq. poured off grain at the beginning) with filtrate. (At this point the preparation can be frozen for use later).
- 6 Add 20g sucrose, 15g Agar then adjust volume to 1 liter.
- 7 Autoclave at 15 psi for 20 minutes.